

Case Based Reasoning Approach for Market Basket Analysis on the Performance of Issuers in the Home Appliances Industry Sector

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Abstract:—The recommendation system (decision support) is an important part of various types of software application development. The recommendation based on a case-based approach aims to overcome the limitations of user insights and to make it easier to provide an overview of item patterns. The study was conducted using five companies in the consumer goods sector in the household appliances sub-sector. The study tested Case Based Reasoning to predict financial conditions and know the association of products to find out the composition patterns in Market Basket Analysis. The research sample is five household appliances sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The value of similiarity of results from case based to predict the company's financial performance in 2019 can be explained using five ratio indicators. The results of the distribution of financial performance descriptions can provide a recommendation system in the form of indentifying companies with hight profits, asset management, product differentiations and explaining the characteristics of companies with low profits.

Keywords: *Case Based Reasoning, Market Basket Analysis, Company Performance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The home appliance industry is predicted to simultaneously increase in line with the development of the property, tourism and hospitality industry in Southeast Asia. In 2014 more than 9.5 million foreign tourists visited Indonesia. In an effort to accommodate the arrival of international tourists to Indonesia, more than 15,000 rooms valued at more than Rp 1.5 trillion were built [1].

As a case in point, a number of households began to buy two-tube washing machines for the first time, while some residents with middle to upper economic levels began to replace washing machines with greater capacity and better technology. National economic growth accompanied by an increase in

purchasing power is a major factor in the predictor of increased sales of household appliances[2].

The increasing challenges of companies in capitalizing the household appliances market, the company's performance becomes quite important. Parameters that can be used in appraising company performance appropriately are by analyzing information from financial statements.

One of technique to determine the association between products is used Market Basket Analysis (MBA). The MBA works by finding combinations of items that often appear together in transaction reports. The function of the MBA is to identify the relationship between consumers and goods purchased [3].

Case Based Reasoning (CBR) is a problem solving paradigm that is closely related to the way of thinking in situations when facing new problems. CBR uses old experience to solve new problems. This research presents an analytical approach and recommendations in cases where company performance is adjusted on the set of items for each product. CBR is the right method because the set of product items in each company is modeled equally.

The recommendation system (decision support) is an important part of various types of software application development. The case-based recommendation approach aims to overcome the limitations of the user's insight and to make it easier to provide an overview of the item's pattern. The recommendation technique tends to give a decision on the similarity of types and patterns of similarity of old cases based on the hypothesis that the value of the item is stable in a certain period of time.

Previous research from Gatzoura and Sanchez-Marre (2015) [4] can analyze consumer behavior revealed from the basketball market structure patterns. An MBA can refer to the search for associations so that it can give meaning to a company's financial performance. In this association, it can also be known patterns of relationships between entity indicators. The study was conducted using five companies engaged in the consumer goods sector household appliances sub-sector. The study examines Case Based Reasoning to find out the similiarity of financial conditions and to know

the association of products to find out the composition patterns in Market Basket Analysis.

II. LITERATURE RIVIEW

This study refers to previous research from Alfonso, Javier, Fernand, Enrique, and Juan on "Energy Optimization Using a Case-Based Reasoning Strategy", in 2018. In this study describes how researchers review problems that occur in several houses and offices in utilizing energy for Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems researchers used the CBR (Case Based Reasoning) method to find solutions to problems associated with forming a multi- architectural system with a wireless sensor network and studying user habits and use of artificial neural networks. This system is considered to be able to save energy by 41% [5].

The next research is from Rahman, Slamet, Darmalaksana, Eclipse and Ramdhani on "Expert System for Deciding a Solution of Mechanical Failure in a Car using Case-based Reasoning" in 2019. In this study discuss the problem of the proper handling of car mechanics for complaints consumers for this research use an expert system with the CBR method to create four functions, namely taking the same problem, reusing knowledge, revising salutions and maintaining experience to strengthen the best solution. This system was built with Object-oriented Software Engineering (OOSE). With the system offered is expected to be able to provide solutions for the mechanics to work in accordance with the problems and also this system can be used for the development of other knowledge [6].

In the two previous studies, researchers studied how to approach the old problem to determine the solution of the problem at this writing, but in this paper is different from the two studies above because this research uses a decision support system as well as the calculation of similarity using the Tversky Method approach.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The stages of the research carried out are as follows;

a. Theoretical Basis

The author conducted a review sourced from reference books, journals and websites to obtain basic theories related to the subject matter to complete this research data.

1) Case Based Reasoning (CBR)

Case-based reasoning (CBR) is the process of solving new problems based on solutions from similar past problems. CBR reasoning is case-based by making analogous solutions. CBR is computer-based reasoning that can solve problems from data distribution in general. CBR development can be continued in the form of prototypes and explored cognitively. CBR is

identical to the rules of induction algorithm in machine learning. CBR begins by identifying a series of cases and training data. The case then forms an implicit generalization and establishes the similarity of characteristics between the case taken with the target problem [7].

Without statistically relevant data to support the generalization of research results there is no guarantee that the CBR process will proceed accordingly. CBR can be developed in a formal statistical framework to form inferences of various cases. Thus the CBR can produce similiarity of new cases with high confidence [8]. The ultimate goal of CBR is to provide enough encoding so that it can be claimed in the form of similiarity.

2) Market Basket Analysis (MBA)

Market Basket Analysis (MBA) is a modeling technique that is based on the concept that if a user uses certain items then there is a limited association then that user is likely to decide to look for these limitations elsewhere. The set of items selected is called "item_set" and the MBA seeks to find associations between users of these items.

IF {X, 0} THEN {0 + Y}

Probability {X, 0} is called "support", conditional probability {0 + Y} is called "confidence". The complexity of an MBA arises when exploiting large amounts of data so detailed transaction items must be available. The main difficulty of the MBA is the many rules that relate to the marketing business. Rules that have minimal support with a high level of trust can be exploited after a solution is obtained.

In financial performance analysis needs to be done impulsively. MBA analysis can provide clues to associations between items so that the main ideas can be obtained. The MBA can be used technically to uncover associations between financial aspects. The MBA works by finding a combination of characteristics that often appear in each aspect.

3) Financial Performance

Financial performance is the result or achievement that has been achieved by the company's management in carrying out its function of managing company assets effectively over a certain period [9]. Financial performance, which is a picture of the financial condition in a certain period both regarding aspects of fund raising and fund distribution, which is usually measured by indicators of capital adequacy, liquidity, and profitability [10].

Financial performance tends to be and definitely measures financial problems. Financial analysis has been very basic and general that serves to assess past

performance by means of analysis looking at the potentials [11]. Financial performance is an analysis conducted to assess the extent to which a company has carried out using the rules of financial implementation properly and correctly [12].

From the literatures that already exists, financial performance is a process or outcome that is very influential on the company, good or bad performance depends on financial analysis looking at its functions. In this study the company's performance indicators are measured from the gross profit ratio, net profit ratio, current asset ratio, debt ratio and total asset turnover.

a) *Gross Profit Ratio (GP)*

Profitability ratio that shows the relationship between gross profit and total revenue on net sales. GP is used to evaluate business operational performance.

b) *Net Profit Ratio (NP)*

The percentage of net profit is the ratio of profit after tax to net sales. NP reveals the remaining profit after all production, administrative and financing costs have been deducted from sales and income tax. NP is one of the best measures of a company's overall results, especially when combined with evaluations using working capital. The size of the NP can be seen from the timeline and compared to the business results of competitors.

c) *Current Assets Ratio (CA)*

Current ratio is a liquidity ratio that measures a company's ability to pay short-term liabilities or within a period of less than one year. CAs can provide investors and analysts with information on how companies can maximize current assets on the balance sheet to meet current debt.

d) *Debt Ratio (DR)*

DR (debt ratio) is a financial ratio that measures the level of corporate leverage. Debt ratio is the ratio of total debt to total assets, expressed in decimal or percentage terms. DR can be interpreted as a proportion of company assets that can be financed by debt.

e) *Total Assets Turnover (AT)*

Total assets turnover is an efficiency ratio that measures a company's ability to generate sales from assets by comparing net sales with the average total assets. AT shows how efficiently a company can use its assets to generate sales.

b. Data Collection

The author uses a quantitative approach with data collection techniques of four household equipment sub-sectors listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, namely: PT Chitose International, PT Kedaung Indah Can, PT Langgeng Makmur Industry and PT Integra Indocabinet.

The profile of each sample entity is explained:

Table 1: Sample 1

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Chitose International
2.	Entity Code Exchange	CINT
3.	Identification number	AA687
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry
5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Group
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Chitose International Tbk was founded in 1979 by producing chairs with high-tech processes in manufacturing. CINT partnered strongly with a Japanese company (Chitose Mfg.Col. ,Ltd) for various types of research, testing and product improvement.

Table 2: Sample 2

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Kedaung Indah Can
2.	Entity Code Exchange	KICI
3.	Identification number	AA177
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry
5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Single
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Kedaung Indah Can was established in 1974 which is one of the manufacturers and exporters of enamel steel cookware. In 2018 KICI is one of the largest pan producers (pans) with a production capacity of 40,000 pots per day with domestic and international markets.

Table 3: Sample 3

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Langgeng Makmur Industry
2.	Entity Code Exchange	LMPI
3.	Identification number	AA213
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry

5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Single
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Langgeng Makmur Industry Tbk is a multinational company that produces household appliances in Sidoarjo Regency. The company was listed on the stock exchange in 1994.

Table 4: Sample 4

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Integra Indocabinet
2.	Entity Code Exchange	WOOD
3.	Identification number	AA767
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry
5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Group
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Integra Indocabinet Tbk is engaged in the furniture and wood production industry as well as conducting import and export trading business. WOOD is a Group type entity that has seven subsidiaries with majority shareholders, PT Integra Indo Lestari (79.31%).

c. Data Collection

The research variables used to analyze company performance are:

- Gros Profit Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Gross\ Profit}{Net\ Sales}$
- Net Profit Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Net\ Profit}{Net\ Sales}$
- Current Asset Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Current\ Asset}{Current\ Liabilities}$
- Debt Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Total\ Liabilities}{Total\ Asset}$
- Total Assets Turnover
Foemula : $\frac{Net\ Sales}{Total\ Asset}$

d. Method of Analysis

The method used in this study is the CBR (Case-Based Reasoning) and MBD (Market Basket Analysis) method with the following stages [13]:

- 1) **Retrieve**
Retrieving the case that most closely resembles the relevance of the new case, the retrieval stage begins by describing some of the problems, and ends if a match is found to the previous problem with the highest level of compatibility. This section refers to the aspects of identification, initial compatibility, search and selection and execution.
- 2) **Reuse**
Reusing the knowledge and information of old cases based on the weight of the most relevant similarities into new cases, resulting in a solution where an adaptation to the new problem might be needed.
- 3) **Revise**
Revisiting the proposed solution is then tested in a real case (simulation). If needed, the solution will be improved to fit the new case.
- 4) **Retain**
Integrate new cases that have succeeded in getting a solution so that it can be used by subsequent cases that are similar to those cases. But if the solution fails, then explain the failure, improve the solution used and test it again.

Figure 1: Case-Based Reasoning Cycle

Market Basket Basket is characterized by the presence of a large number of product items from related companies. The aim of the MBA is to capture the presence or absence of products in the concept of competitive financial performance between companies. The stages of the MBA process are as follows:

- a) **Load Transaction**
Contains transaction data transaction id, characteristic id, and number of entities. The data shows a certain value contained in the aspects of the predicate of financial performance.

b) Edit, Transform and Load (ETL)

Process aggregation functions using Structure Query Language (SQL). The association was formed from GROUP BY and HAVING. Transform is used to rotate ExampleSet by grouping several samples from the same group into one channel. A set of attributes can then be renamed according to the specified property. Missing values in the sample can be replaced with the RMV (Replace Missing Value) operator.

c) FP-Growth

The FP-Growth operator can efficiently calculate the entire set of items from a given ExampleSet using the FP-tree data structure.

d) Create Association Rules

Make association rules that can be used to recommend items that have been trusted according to the rules.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the financial ratios of each company listed are as follows:

Table 5: Financial Statement 2017 (Case Based)

Year	Entity			
	CINT	KICI	LMPI	WOOD
2017				
Gross Profit	1.252	29	81	561
Net Sales	374	113	411	1.735
Net Profit	34	8	31	171
Current Asset	211	90	572	1.666
Current Liabilities	66	124	360	1.485
Total Liabilitas	94	58	458	1.930
Total Assets	477	149	835	3.843

*(in billions of rupiah)

The financial statement value is obtained from the analysis of the annual year report of each company in the household equipment sub sector.

Table 6: Financial Statement 2018 (New Case)

Year	Entity			
	CINT	KICI	LMPI	WOOD
2018				
Gross Profit	113	19	50	739
Net Sales	370	87	456	2.101
Net Profit	30	4	46	242
Current Asset	220	97	526	2.326
Current Liabilities	81	16	380	1.834
Total Liabilitas	103	59	456	2.138
Total Assets	491	154	787	4.588

*(in billions of rupiah)

In the financial statement for 2017 - 2018, seven items of report on the company's financial position and profit and loss are presented.

Table 7: Product Line Issuer

Issuer	Manufacturer
CINT	Furniture
KICI	Cooking ware
LMPH	Household appience (alumanium)
WOOD	Wood product

Then the method for calculating similarity is using the tversky method. Tversky method is a method in calculating similarity that is used to calculate the similarity of two objects (items) that are binary. In looking for old cases that have similarities with new cases, the concept of similarity will be used.

$$SIM(X, Y) = 1 - DIST(X, Y)$$

$$= 1 - \sqrt{\sum_1^n \delta(X_i, X_2)^2}$$

$$\delta(X_1, X_2) = \frac{|X_i - Y_i|}{|min_i - max_i|}$$

X = new case
Y = case based
Xi = case attribute x
Yi = case attribute y

The results of the K most similar cases are followed by the Market Basket Analysis model:

i_{j1}		i_{jt}
$i_{(j+k-1)1}$		$i_{(j+k-1)t}$

Figure 2: FP-Tree Analysis Market Basket

The lines of each issuer are explained in table 3 that the company's market movements are in a line that is almost similar (Similiarity) which is described in figure 3 below :

Figure 3. Similiarity Product Market

PT Chitose Internasional Tbk, and PT Integra Indocabinet Tbk. Has the same sector in manufacturing furniture type processing. PT Kedaug Indah Can Tbk. And PT Langgeng Makmur Industry Tbk. Have a common sector in the processing of household appliance manufacturing.

Table 8: Chitos Internasional (CINT)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,334808283	0,306279351
Net Profit	0,091970761	0,081133973
Current Asset	0,197877605	0,209009386
Debt	0,784668987	0,753773459
Total Assets Turnover	0,334808283	0,306279351

The financial ratio of the issuer of the CINT code is obtained by decreasing the gross profit ratio which affect the net profit value. Current assets in 2018 increased followed by a decrease in the debt ratio, but simultaneously asset turnover decrease due to the transfer of ownership and depreciation.

Table 9: Kedaug Indah Can (KICI)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,25597157	0,216414649
Net Profit	0,070069533	0,046307908
Current Asset	0,387642665	0,38574618
Debt	0,759032978	0,564065596
Total Assets Turnover	0,25597157	0,216414649

The KICI issuers'ratio declined in gross profit and net profit. On the scale of assets in 2018 no significant changes were seen. The debt ratio decreases followed by a decrease in total assets.

Table 10: Langgeng Makmur Industry (LMPI)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,196516248	0,109020311
Net Profit	0,075741214	0,100461123
Current Asset	0,549149768	0,579905087
Debt	0,492654683	0,579068523
Total Assets Turnover	0,196516248	0,109020311

Langgeng Makmur Industry, companies with LMPI code experienced a decrease in gross profit, but in terms of net profit increased due to the efficiency of net sales that can minimize transportation costs and sales commissions. Asset in 2018 are added as the debt ratio increases.

Table 11: Integra Indocabinet (WOOD)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,323298582	0,351724153
Net Profit	0,098824921	0,115161898
Current Asset	0,502309903	0,466047532
Debt	0,451392465	0,457988106
Total Assets TurnOver	0,323298582	0,351724153

Integra Indocabinet shows an increase in gross profit and net profit. Assets in 2018 are reduced, debt increases and total assets simultaneously increase in the valuation of land and buildings.

Table 12: Similarity in The Performance of Furniture Issues

Ratio	CINT X_i	WOOD Y_i	2019 Similarity
Gross Profit	0,306	0,352	0,329
Net Profit	0,081	0,115	0,098
Current Asset	0,209	0,466	0,338
Debt	0,754	0,458	0,606
Total Assets Turnover	0,306	0,352	0,329

Chitose Internasioal which experienced a decrease in gross and net profit was inversely proportional to the value recorded by the issuer Integra Indocabinet. The two entities have similarities in the terms of the type of furniture market caps.

Figure 4: Issuer Furniture Performance

Overall Similarity of furniture product sales performance in 2019 in terms of value of similarity has not been able to provide an increase in valuation. This can be analyzed from the capital structure of the two entities with relatively different differences.

Table 13. Similarity in the Performance of Household Appliances Issues

Ratio	KICI X_i	LMPI Y_i	2019 Similarity
Gross Profit	0,216	0,109	0,163
Net Profit	0,046	0,100	0,073
Current Asset	0,386	0,580	0,483
Debt	0,564	0,579	0,572
Assets Turnover	0,216	0,109	0,163

Each industry has an average similarity value <0.5 so that the predicted performance in 2019 can be adjusted based on 2017 to 2018.

Figure 5 : Issuer Household Appliance Performance

Based on a case based analysis to determine the value similarity in each financial ratio, it is found that there is a strong similarity between the market share of CINT and WOOD issuers.

Stages of Market Basket Analysis

Market Basket is used to analyze associations between corporate entities by determining the set of financial performance to build association rules to obtain a recommendation reference.

Figure 6 : Market Basket Process

In the initial stage, load transactions are analyzed based on the synthetic value of the case based performance of each company. Then financial data is generated based on entity channels. Pivot tables are used so that each case based result consists of binary rows. After the pivot process, changes in financial ratios become indicators on a category scale.

Table 14: Market Basket Indeks

Entity	Profit			Asset		Dif	
	R	Sd	T	S	B	Y	N
CINT	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
KICI	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
LMPI	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
WOOD	0	0	1	0	1	0	0

Using the FP-Growth function, a set of items is determined for each entity. Set items that show financial performance which has the most dominant value. The results of the binary market basket are obtained from financial performance ratios.

Table 15: Value Probability Indeks

Rule	Confidence	LaPlace	Gain	Lift
1.	1	1	-0.50	2
2.	1	1	-0.50	2
7.	1	1	-0.25	4
8.	1	1	-0.25	4
11.	1	1	-0.25	4
12.	1	1	-0.25	4
15.	1	1	-0.25	4
16.	1	1	-0.25	4
17.	1	1	-0.25	4
18.	1	1	-0.25	4

The results of data processing using Rapidminer obtained a large number of set rules. In this study the rule is only displayed on the value of confidence and the value of LaPlace = 1 (meet the requirements). The premise value is obtained from the basketball market index and the conclusion value is obtained from the value probability index.

Table 16: Market Basket Recommendation

Rule	Premises	Conclusion
1	Hight Profit	Many assets
2	Many assets	Hight Profit
7	No differentiation	Low profit
8	Low profit	No differentiation
11	Few assets, Product differentiation	Moderate profit
12	Moderate profit	Few assets, Product differentiation
15	No differentiation	Few assets Low profit
16	Few assets, No differentiation	Low profit
17	Low profit	Few assets No differentiation
18	Few assets, Low profit	No differentiation

The final results of the basketball market calculation obtained 11 main rules that show the premise and conclusion results from the case base of the performance of household appliances sub-sector companies listed on the

Stock Exchange.

Discussion

Household appliances sub-sector companies that have high profit predicate are explained in graph 5 with rule 10 and rule 2. Companies with high profit have good product differentiation criteria and adequate company assets. Rules 1 and 9 explain the prediction scenario for companies that have large amounts of assets. The higher the asset, the more product differentiation and the increase in profit is easier to achieve.

Product differentiation is pinned on companies that have various types of product choices vary according to customer needs. If product differentiation can absorb market potential, it cannot ensure profitability. Product differentiation in household appliances sub-sector companies is also not lineary related to the amount of ownership of asset. Companies that have low profits are caused by lack of asset and insufficiency product differentiation. This was explained by the 7th and 15th Basket Market Rule.

A limitation of the results of the recommendations on the CBR and MBA methodologies is the use of new items or types of objects that are less popular which causes too high specialization in the decisions produced. CBR and MBA methods tend to ignore structures that underlie user preferences with a lack of evaluation of the decisions obtained. This study overcomes these obstacles by calculating probabilities with varying distributions to indicate a higher level of knowledge.

V. CONCLUSION

Research on the performance of the issuers of the household appliances subsector industry with the Case Based Reasoning and Market Basket Analysis approach obtained the following conclusions: The similiarity value of the case based results to predict the company's financial performance in 2019 can be explained using five ratio indicators. The results of the distribution of financial performance can provide a system of recommendations in the form of identification of companies with high profits, asset management, product differentiation and explain the characteristics of companies with low profits.

VI. SUGGESTION

Researchers suggest to develop a financial-based recommendation system to predict the company's performance in the coming year. The flow of financial ratio analysis can be processed into data mining to provide recommendations to the public in reaching investment access on the Stock Exchange.

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